

Influence of moisture content on the results of penetration and withdrawal resistance measurements on softwoods

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Abstract: Needle penetration resistance (NPR) and screw withdrawal resistance (SWR) are widely used techniques for density estimation of woods integrated in timber structures. The moisture content (MC) influences these measurements and correction coefficients are needed to ensure the accuracy of results. The goal of the present paper was to scrutinize the relation between NPR and SWR measurements and MC in case of radiata pine, Scots pine, Salzmänn pine, and maritime pine usually used in wood constructions, from which 25 specimens from each species were probed. The specimen's MC ranged from 65.1 to 8.3%. Results show that NPR depth has a positive linear relationship with MC while the SWR force a negative one below the fiber saturation point (FSP). Above the FSP the MC influence is less pronounced and less regular. MC correction factors of measurements below the FSP are proposed for the species studied.

Keywords: Moisture content (MC), nondestructive testing (NDT), needle penetration resistance (NPR), probing, screw withdrawal resistance (SWR)

Introduction

Density estimation of woods integrated in existing timber structures is usually performed by nondestructive testing (NDT) probing methods, such as needle and drill penetration resistance as well as screw and nail withdrawal resistance (Görlacher 1987; Rinn et al. 1996; Bobadilla et al. 2007; Esteban et al. 2009; Ponneth et al. 2014). A similar approach is the resistance drilling technique (Oliveira et al. 2017). Wood hardness is strongly associated with density (Ceccotti and Togni 1996). The methods of needle penetration resistance (NPR) and screw withdrawal resistance (SWR) are also suitable in combination with other NDT methodologies for MOE and MOR estimation (Divós and Tanaka 1997; Ishiguri et al. 2008). Ponneth et al. (2014) found that the NPR data correlate well with static bending MOE and MOR. However, SWR alone is inadequate for MOE and MOR estimation (Meierhofer 1988). According to Carballo et al. (2009) and Casado et al. (2012), the most common probing techniques in Spain are NPR, which is performed by the Pilodyn 6J Forest device, and SWR by means of the Screw Withdrawal Resistance Meter (SWRM) device. These approaches are in focus of the present study. The NPR technique relies on shooting a pin into wood with a constant energy, and the penetration depth is read on a scale. It is also common for grading of standing trees (Cown 1978), evaluation of poles (Morrel et al. 1994), and assessment of woods integrated in wood engineering structures (Görlacher 1987). The basic of the SWR technique is the withdrawing of a standard screw (previously screwed into the wood) and measuring the withdrawal force (Divós et al. 1994).

There is no clear agreement in the literature about the measurement differences between radial (R) and tangential (T) direction. Cockrell (1933) studied SWR in ten species (basswood, beech, birch, black ash, hemlock, red oak, red pine, red spruce, sugar maple and white pine) and found differences between SWR_R and SWR_T depending on species with $SWR_T > SWR_R$ in 6 species, and in four species the opposite was true. This difference between R and T forces was more important in

dry wood than in green wood. Bues (1987) found differences between R and T nail withdrawal forces of pine species, but no differences were found in SWR tests. Bobadilla et al. (2007) found no significant differences between NPR_R and NPR_T and SWR_R and SWR_T on large cross-sections of Spanish radiata, Scots and Salzmänn pine. Íñiguez (2007) and Calderón (2012) could not find differences between R and T measurements on dry woods, either. NPR and SWR results of Martínez (2016) on 10 species were the R and T measurements also very similar.

Íñiguez-González et al. (2015) showed that several factors affect NDT (based on ultrasound waves, impact stress waves, longitudinal vibration, SWR, NPR and drill penetration resistance), and one of the most relevant parameters was MC. NDTs are also applied for woods integrated in outdoor engineering constructions and thus the influence of MC can be very high. Hoffmeyer (1978) tested several Pilodyn prototype instruments (equipped with different diameter needles and 6, 9, 12 and 18 J energy release) on Norway spruce, Scots pine and European beech. An increase of 1 to 2% in penetration depth per 1% MC increment was found in the 8 to 24% MC range. However, the increase was extremely low above 30% MC. Smith and Morrell (1986) used Pilodyn 6J and Pilodyn 18J devices on 106 Douglas fir samples with 50 x 50 mm² cross-section with densities of 400 to 500 kg m⁻³. In the MC range from 6 to 30%, a mean increase of 0.19 mm (2.03%) in NPR depth per 1% MC increment and 0.26 mm (1.41%) was reported, respectively. However, no correlation was seen above 30% MC. Görlacher (1987) tested the Pilodyn 6J device on 208 Norway spruce specimens with 35 x 150 mm² cross-section and with 450 mm length. A 0.73% penetration depth increment per 1% MC increase was detected in the 12 to 21% MC range. On the other hand, Calderón (2012) did not find any variation of NPR deepness on Scots pine, radiata pine and Salzmänn pine in the MC range of 8 to 14%. The coefficients of variation (COV) were high. The same author also tested the MC effect on SWR and found increasing SWR forces with decreasing MC, and proposed a second order correction equation to describe the effect. Other authors also confirmed the high sensitivity of SWR techniques to MC (McLain 1997). Cockrell (1933) estimated the SWR force at 7% MC to be on average 50% higher than above the FSP, and there were species dependent differences: for rock maple it was by 71% and for yellow pine by 23% higher.

The present study is a continuation of the research of Llana et al. (2017), in which the NDT methods working with ultrasound (two devices), impact stress waves (one device) and longitudinal vibrations (two devices) were comparatively investigated for radiata pine, Scots pine, Salzmänn pine, and maritime pine. Here the NPR and SWR tests will be revisited and results should be checked again as a function of MC from the same wood species, which are frequently applied in engineering wood constructions in Spain. The expectation is that more reliable data can be collected than before and that some contradicting literature data can be elucidated.

Materials and methods

Materials: The following wood species with the following dimensions were tested: 100 planed 500 mm long 100 x 150 mm² cross-section specimens of radiata pine (*Pinus radiata* D. Don), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), Salzmänn pine (*Pinus nigra* Arnold ssp. *salzmannii* (Dunal) Franco), and maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster* Ait. ssp. *mesogeensis* Fieschi & Gaussen) of Spanish provenance. Wet specimens were selected in the sawmill and their ends were sealed to promote uniform drying (Figure 1a).

NDT experiments: NDTs were performed by means of needle penetration resistance (NPR) and screw withdrawal resistance (SWR) techniques. The tests were repeated at 7 to 14 different MC stages during the air drying process, depending on the species. The first measurements were done at the initial wet condition, with an average MC of 57.8% (radiata pine), 46.5% (Scots pine), 65.1% (Salzmänn pine), and 47.1% (maritime pine). The last measurements were taken at the final dry condition of 8.9, 10.0, 8.3, and 8.5% mean MC, respectively. Air drying needed 135, 131, 181, and 178 days, respectively, to complete this process. The variables: 1) NPR depth (mm) obtained by the commercial device Pilodyn 6 J Forest (Proceq, Schwerzenbach, Switzerland) (Figure 1b). This works with a calibrated spring that releases a 2.5 mm diameter steel needle with a constant energy of 6 J. 2) SWR force (kN), obtained by the commercial device SWR Meter (Fakopp Enterprise Bt.,

Sopron, Hungary) (Figure 1c). The instrument was equipped with a standard Heco-Fix plus screw with a Spax (PZD) type head. This is a yellow zinc plated 70 mm long screw with 4-mm-diameter, and has a penetration depth of 20 mm. Areas close to the pith and other singularities such as knots, resin pockets, etc. were avoided, and successive tests were performed along the same grain and with at least a 30 mm gap between them. The R or T directions were not taken into account, in agreement with the literature data as referred to in the Introduction.

Determination of the mean moisture content (MC): The oven dry method according to standard EN 13183-1 (2002) was applied. Specimen dimensions and mass (Mettler Toledo, Greifensee, Switzerland) were recorded at every MC stage to obtain density. After the last measurement, whole specimens were dried in an oven [Dry Big 2002971, (JP Selecta, Abrera, Spain)] and the MC was calculated according to the EN 13183-1 (2002) method. The formation of a MC gradient profile cannot be excluded, thus the applied methods allows only for the determination of a mean MC.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the mean values and COVs of MC, density, NPR depths and SWR forces for the species at different MC stages. MC mean values varied from values above the FSP (57.8, 46.5, 65.1, and 47.1% for radiata pine, Scots pine, Salzmänn pine and maritime pine, respectively) to dry values (8.9, 10.0, 8.3, and 8.5% in the same order, respectively). At the beginning of the tests, MC and density values were widely dispersed and variable. Mean values of NPR depth and SWR force varied depending on species, and COV were similar from the first to the last measurements.

Expectedly, the higher the MCs, the greater are NPR depths and lower SWR forces. Different NPR data are typical for the species, and comparing the data obtained from the driest values, there is a clear relation (the higher the density, the less is the penetration depth), except in the case of radiata pine, which has the lowest density (485 kg m^{-3}) and the lowest penetration depth (10 mm). The forest management of radiata pine is very peculiar (Sanchez et al. 2003). It is felled after ca. 25 y as a fast growing species. It contains therefore a large amount of juvenile wood (with lower density) and little mature wood (higher density). NPR depth was measured in the external part (as usual in structural assessments), where usually the mature wood is. The same explanation is true for SWR forces in radiata pine.

The influence of MC on NPR

Figure 2a shows the linear relationships above and below the FSP. Above FSP, only the Salzmänn pine (four measurements) gives rise to considerable results, and otherwise, the MC influence is almost negligible. Similar observations were made by Hoffmeyer (1978) and Smith and Morrell (1986). The data above the FSP for the other species are statistically not relevant. The results between 10 to 30 % are reliable, which show similar positive linear and species dependent relationships. The NPR depth values significantly differ between species-density, but the slope of the correlation lines can be considered as approx. parallel. Thus calculations for the MC range below 30% can be done for all species with Eq. 1:

$$\text{Depth} = 0.23 * \text{MC} - 1.28 * Z_{\text{rad}} + 2.68 * Z_{\text{sco}} + 1.85 * Z_{\text{sal}} + 9.00;$$

$$R^2 = 40.26\%, \text{ P-value} = 0.00 \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

Where: *Depth* (mm) obtained by Pilodyn 6J Forest instrument; Z_{rad} , Z_{sco} and Z_{sal} are the constants for radiata pine, Scots pine and Salzmänn pine, respectively, which are only equal to 1 for the tree in question, and for maritime pine are equal to 0. As the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship between penetration depth and MC at a 95.0% confidence level. An increase of 0.23 mm in penetration depth was found for each 1% MC increment in the 10 to 30% range of MC. This value is slightly higher than the 0.19 mm value proposed by other authors for Douglas fir (Smith and Morrell 1986).

The influence of MC on SWR

In Figure 2b, two clearly different linear relationships were found for the MC range above and below the FSP. In the case of Salzmänn pine (the only species with enough data above the FSP), the

MC influence above FSP was much lower than below FSP. Once again, SWR forces show similar negative linear regression slopes for the studied species. In the same way as for NPR depth, only one model is proposed because the slopes of the correlation curves below FSP can be considered as nearly parallel (Eq. 2)..

$$Force = -0.05 \cdot MC - 0.11 \cdot Z_{rad} - 0.59 \cdot Z_{sco} - 0.42 \cdot Z_{sal} + 2.99;$$
$$R^2 = 51.29\%, \quad P\text{-value} = 0.00 \text{ (Eq. 2)}$$

Where: *Force* (kN) obtained by the SWRM instrument; Z_{rad} , Z_{sco} and Z_{sal} are for radiata pine, Scots pine and Salzmann pine, respectively, which are only equal to 1 for the tree in question, and for maritime pine they are equal to 0. As the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship between SWR force and MC at a 95.0% confidence level. A decrease of 0.05 kN in SWR force was found per 1% MC increment in the MC range 10 to 30%. This value is just within the limit range from 0.05 kN to 0.15 kN obtained by Calderón (2012) for radiata pine, Scots pine and Salzmann pine.

Correction factors for MC

To achieve comparable results with other works, measurement values must be corrected to a standard MC reference value, that is usually 12% (chamber conditions of 65% RH and 20°C). From the linear regressions (Eq. 1 and 2), correction factors were calculated for 12% MC by means of the Eqs. 3 and 4.

$$Depth_{12\%MC} = Depth_{MC} / [1 + k_{MC} \cdot (MC - 12)] \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

$$Force_{12\%MC} = Force_{MC} / [1 - k_{MC} \cdot (MC - 12)] \text{ (Eq. 4)}$$

Where: $Depth_{12\%MC}$ (mm) obtained by Pilodyn 6J Forest NPR instrument; $Depth_{MC}$ (mm) at a given MC; $Force_{12\%MC}$ (kN) obtained by the SWRM instrument; $Force_{MC}$ (kN) is a given MC; k_{MC} correction factors, which are listed in Table 2.

In the case of the Pilodyn 6J Forest device, an increase from 1.6 to 2.2% in NPR depth was found per 1% MC increment in the MC range of 10 to 30%. These values were slightly higher than the ones proposed by other authors for other coniferous species, i.e. 0.73% for Norway spruce (Görlacher 1987) and in the 1 to 2% range for Norway spruce, Scots pine and European beech (Hoffmeyer 1978). In the case of the SWRM device, a decrease from 2.1 to 2.8% in SWR force was found per 1% MC increment in the MC range of 10 to 30%.

The differences in comparison with literature data are partly species dependent, and are partly due to other factors such as the growing conditions of the trees (place, micro- and macroclimate), MC determination method, influence of the device used, which is especially important for SWRM, where hand turn velocity affects measurements, and the natural heterogeneity of wood in general. Although both devices show optically different trends, Table 2 reveals that the influence of MC is similar concerning the species. MC has more influence on the SWR force than in NPR depth in case of Scots pine and Salzmann pine.

Conclusions

NPR depths and SWR forces measured in four Spanish sourced pine woods (radiata pine, Scots pine, Salzmann pine and maritime pine) can be generalized by two different linear relationships as a function of MC. The slope is steeper below the FSP than above, in agreement with the literature. NPR depth obtained by the Pilodyn 6J Forest device shows a positive relationship with MC changes, increasing 0.23 mm up to the FSP (in the 10-30% range) per % MC change. However, in the same MC range, SWR force obtained by the SWRM device had a negative relationship with MC changes, i.e. decreasing 0.05 kN per % MC change. Correction factors below FSP (in the 10-30% range) were determined for a 12% reference MC, varying from 1.6 to 2.2% for NPR depth and from 2.1 to 2.8% for SWR force, depending on the species. The sensitivity of both devices to MC changes is similar for radiata pine and maritime pine. However, SWR sensitivity is higher in case of Scots pine and Salzmann pine.

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Table 1: Averaged data of MCs, densities, needle penetration resistance (NPR) depths and screw withdrawal resistance (SWR) forces for different wood species.

Wood	Stages	Days	MC		Density		NPR depth		SWR force	
			(%)	COV (%)	kg m ⁻³	COV (%)	(mm)	COV (%)	(kN)	COV (%)
Radiata pine	1	0	57.8	50.77	662	23.86	16	16.85	1.65	14.99
	2	14	31.6	48.21	559	16.84	14	14.19	1.78	18.17
	3	31	20.2	21.08	517	11.39	12	16.89	1.85	15.98
	4	45	16.4	11.82	508	10.35	11	18.99	1.92	16.48
	5	73	12.4	7.98	497	10.04	10	16.09	2.14	18.61
	6	94	10.9	6.09	492	9.75	10	16.18	2.21	17.08
	7	135	8.9	5.46	485	9.77	10	14.57	2.41	19.14
Scots pine	1	0	46.5	40.20	629	10.53	22	14.42	1.04	13.31
	2	6	30.9	36.22	572	6.85	19	15.90	1.15	13.38
	3	22	22.1	21.82	537	4.26	17	19.15	1.32	12.23
	4	48	16.0	7.51	524	4.31	15	15.79	1.51	11.39
	5	58	14.4	5.48	522	4.35	15	15.78	1.64	14.38
	6	76	12.3	4.74	514	4.67	14	14.15	1.67	15.02
	7	92	11.1	4.46	515	4.40	14	17.79	1.75	16.92
	8	131	10.0	5.02	510	4.66	13	14.83	1.79	15.28
Salzmann pine	1	0	65.1	41.55	816	17.40	18	16.82	0.77	26.49
	2	6	57.4	44.33	775	17.17	17	17.53	0.68	23.84
	3	14	45.0	46.61	714	15.17	17	19.65	0.76	25.19
	4	20	37.8	46.06	695	13.50	17	20.55	0.81	32.39
	5	34	26.0	40.49	644	11.00	16	18.21	1.32	23.38
	6	49	19.7	31.07	616	10.40	15	20.85	1.42	24.02
	7	56	17.7	26.14	609	10.51	15	21.98	1.52	20.67
	8	62	15.7	24.16	603	10.02	14	18.87	1.70	19.89
	9	72	14.5	18.27	595	10.17	14	19.27	1.86	19.84
	10	87	13.3	25.68	596	10.23	14	18.24	1.93	18.71
	11	105	10.9	9.20	587	10.66	13	17.04	2.04	20.19
	12	126	9.7	7.34	581	10.85	13	17.47	2.15	19.75
	13	142	9.0	6.33	580	10.99	13	15.54	2.20	19.31
	14	181	8.3	5.84	580	10.74	12	15.87	2.35	19.00
Maritime pine	1	0	47.1	34.61	699	9.53	18	18.29	1.65	16.12
	2	28	22.5	14.41	596	7.36	14	16.25	1.82	17.30
	3	41	18.9	10.33	586	6.82	13	17.00	1.95	17.25
	4	58	16.4	7.91	579	6.99	13	18.14	2.06	17.06
	5	72	14.7	6.95	577	7.04	12	17.68	2.11	17.53
	6	100	11.8	5.32	569	7.04	12	17.13	2.27	18.94
	7	121	10.5	5.54	565	7.09	12	18.77	2.39	16.88
	8	162	8.6	4.75	559	7.01	11	18.73	2.56	17.39
	9	178	8.5	5.09	564	7.09	11	17.64	2.65	18.61

Table 2: Correction factors (k_{MC}) in % obtained for the wood species indicated based on the NPR and SWR approaches (below FSP).

Wood	k_{MC} (%)	
	NPR depth	SWR force
Radiata pine	2.2	2.2
Scots pine	1.6	2.8
Salzmann pine	1.7	2.5
Maritime pine	2.0	2.1

Figure 1: Illustration of the materials and instruments used. a) Specimens with sealed ends. b) The Pilodyn 6J Forest instrument based on the needle penetration resistance (NPR). c) The screw withdrawal resistance meter (SWRM) instrument

Figure 2: a) NPR depth data as a function of % MC. b) SWR force as a function of % MC.